

SOUNDSKETCHER: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF SOUND BASED ON CROSSMODAL AUDIOVISUAL CORRESPONDENCES

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ABSTRACT

Alternative notation systems like graphical notation emerged in the 20th century reshaping the link between sound and score. Soundsketcher explores this through aural scores, visually representing sound objects based on perceptual and cognitive principles. Unlike existing tools, it enhances automation and user customization. Soundsketcher relies on established audiovisual cross-modal correspondences. It extracts audio features such as spectral centroid, pitch, loudness, and periodicity, mapping them to visual elements; feature combinations (rather than only one-to-one mappings) are employed to enhance perceptual accuracy of graphical representations. The system also explores the potential of AI models to automated segmentation, using Wav2Vec 2.0 embeddings for temporal segmentation through vector similarity analysis, and CLAP for semantic identification of sound objects. Examples are provided to demonstrate Soundsketcher’s potential for sound visualization, analysis, and creative graphical notation in electronic and experimental music.

1. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of electronic, experimental, and improvised music during the 20th century expanded the boundaries of musical sound and expression. Since this music challenges the norms of traditional music and notation, alternative forms of representation, like graphical notation, emerged, reshaping the connection between musical sound and the score. Three different approaches to understanding and utilizing graphic scores have been identified by Matsigkou et al. [1]: a) as a tool for depicting recorded or synthesized sound objects, particularly within electronic music contexts, b) as a means of encouraging open creative communication among performers, especially in experimental and improvised music, and c) as a facilitative medium for enhancing collaboration between researchers and participants from diverse backgrounds in interdisciplinary and applied research. All these approaches are explored in the context of the [Soundsketcher project](#).

In the current paper, we focus on the first approach, namely, graphic notation as a means for representing sound objects. We will use the term ‘aural score’ (rather than graphic score) to refer to a score generated retrospectively
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using graphic notation as a means to represent potential “reduced listening” experience of an electronic piece (see Subsection 2.1). The paper presents an attempt to determine a collection or combination of cognitively relevant acoustic features mapped to graphic features based on established cross-modal audiovisual correspondences. The resulting “sound sketch” can be seen as a cognitively pertinent reduction or summary of an audio spectrogram. Towards the end of the paper, the identification of sound objects via deep learning techniques will be briefly addressed, as a way to complement and enrich graphic representation.

Soundsketcher aims to offer a cognitively inspired ‘translation’ of sound into visual elements. The proposed system relies on audio signal analysis and sound feature extraction (see Subsection 3.3 and Section 4). The incoming audio signal is segmented into small frames from which specific audio features are extracted. Each of these frames corresponds to a single vertical line (properties such as line length, width, angle, color saturation) in the visual representation with its properties determined by the extracted audio features (such as spectral centroid, F0, loudness, zero crossing rate, periodicity, etc.). Existing research on cross-modal correspondences (see Subsection 2.2) provides insights into how auditory and visual attributes relate. Soundsketcher is designed to provide a default mapping based on established cross-modal studies, offering, at the same time, users the flexibility to customize these mappings according to their preferences. This dual approach provides a cognitively based foundation while allowing creative freedom, enabling users to explore innovative methods of visualizing sound.

A significant challenge for Soundsketcher arises in regards to stream separation, which involves the identification and representation of distinct sound sources and auditory streams within a complex audio environment. Acousmatic music usually involves multiple overlapping streams, merged into a single audio file. While deep learning techniques for source separation exist, they often underperform outside specific contexts like popular music, where models are trained on isolated instrument tracks such as bass, vocals, and drums. We anticipate that Soundsketcher will soon be able to integrate advanced AI auditory scene analysis systems. Currently, it is designed to handle audio consisting of a single auditory stream or multiple ‘monophonic’ streams.

In addition to employing signal processing techniques, we are currently exploring machine learning techniques, including the use of CLAP and Wav2Vec 2.0 embeddings,

with a view to grouping audio segments into distinct sound objects and enabling semantic identification of these objects (see Subsections 3.4 and 3.5). As the technology evolves, we anticipate integrating advanced machine learning models capable of handling diverse musical contexts, thereby expanding the tool’s versatility and accuracy in representing complex auditory environments.

Soundsketcher aims not only to automate sound visualization but also to contribute to the broader discourse on how we perceive, analyze, and represent sound in visual forms, along with exploring the ways we generate and use creatively graphic notation in collaborative experimental music settings.

2. SOUND VISUALISATION

2.1 Aural scores

Aural scores are a form of graphical sound representation that prioritize listening-based interpretation over performance instruction. As Schröder notes, they are produced a posteriori, visualizing sound events to support analytical listening and understanding. [2] Aural scores are particularly relevant for electroacoustic and acousmatic music, where traditional notation falls short in representing the spectral, textural, and temporal complexities of the medium.

There is a rich tradition of graphic music representation, with various approaches emerging to address the challenges of notating non-standard sound materials. In particular, Denis Smalley’s theory of spectromorphology [3] has played a fundamental role in shaping how listeners analyze and interpret electroacoustic music, introducing key perceptual concepts such as spectral density, motion, and morphological articulation. Recent efforts to support the transcription of such music include software tools and visualization systems (see Subsection 2.3), while conferences like TENOR (Technologies for Music Notation and Representation) offer valuable resources and research on alternative notational strategies for contemporary and experimental sound practices [4].

2.2 Cross-modal correspondences

The inherent associations between different sensory modalities are known as cross-modal correspondences. Grounding a framework for mapping sounds to visual forms on well-documented audiovisual associations has the potential to produce graphic representations that resonate with the listening experience. The relevant literature (see here for recent reviews [5, 6]) provides several starting points, including the positive association between pitch and loudness with vertical elevation, the inverse relationship between pitch and physical size, and the positive one between loudness and size. Moreover, high frequencies are often associated with brighter colors and sharper shapes, whereas low frequencies correspond to darker colors and rounder forms. Additionally, timbral qualities such as brightness, lightness, warmth, harshness and softness have been systematically associated with color hues and properties of shapes [7, 8]. Table 1 compiles some of the

Table 1. Guidelines for mapping auditory dimensions to visual qualities with indicative references. (+) indicates a positive relationship, and (−) a negative one.

Auditory Dimension	Visual Qualities
Pitch	elevation(+) [9], size(-) [10], angularity (+) [11], light intensity (+) [12]
Loudness	size(+) [13], elevation(+) [14], brightness(+), light intensity (+) [12], colour saturation (+) [15]
High-frequency content/ Brightness	angularity(+), brightness (+) [16, 17], yellow colour (+) [18], light colours (+) [8]
Roughness/Noisiness/Harshness	angularity (+), red (+), yellow (+), dark gray (+), blue (-), green (-), light gray (-) [7], colour saturation (+) [15]
Dissonance	angularity (+) [19]

most established relationships between auditory and visual concepts.

2.3 Tools and applications

A number of tools have been developed to support the construction of graphical representations of sound, each offering unique functionalities tailored to different analytical and creative contexts [4]. Some tools, such as Acousmographe [20] and eAnalysis [21], integrate FFT-based spectral representations with manual annotation capabilities, allowing users to add visual elements for interpretation and analysis. Others, like Partiels [22] and Sonic Visualiser [23], emphasize detailed extraction of spectral and temporal features, focusing more on representing acoustic properties rather than providing perceptually pertinent graphic annotations of sound events. In addition to these, Grill and Flexer’s system [24] presents an automated approach to sound visualization, specifically targeting the representation of textures. By analyzing spectral and temporal features, it generates visualizations that reflect the perceived qualities of sound textures, offering an alternative to manual annotation.

While many sound visualization tools have contributed to the field, most still rely heavily on manual input, limiting accessibility and efficiency. Automated methods, like Grill and Flexer’s system for texture representation, reduce manual effort but struggle with the dynamic nature of music. Since sound evolves over time with fluctuations in pitch, timbre, and intensity, an effective visualization must account for these temporal attributes.

3. THE SOUNDSKETCHER TOOL

3.1 Aims and scope

The aim of Soundsketcher is to develop an automated system for transforming auditory features into meaningful visual representations, bridging the gap between sound analysis and graphical interpretation. By reducing reliance on manual annotation, the system seeks to provide a more efficient and accessible tool for composers, researchers and

sound designers working with sound structures. By visually mapping sound characteristics, it serves as a valuable educational tool, supporting students and educators in exploring sound perception, music analysis, and audiovisual relationships [25]. Furthermore, it can be a valuable annotation tool for music therapists, helping them track and analyze improvisatory communication with clients during therapy sessions [26].

Overall, Soundsketcher facilitates automatic visualization while also enabling users to modify and customize the mappings, offering flexibility in representing auditory features to suit diverse analytical and creative needs.

3.2 Design Principles

The design of Soundsketcher is guided by three core principles that together shape its functionality and user experience. First, *automation* is a key focus, with the tool automating the conversion of sound into visual representations, significantly reducing the need for manual input. This allows users to concentrate more on interpreting the visuals and exploring creative possibilities. Second, the principle of *perceptual relevance* ensures that the visual outputs are meaningfully aligned with the auditory experience (see Subsection 2.2). This is achieved through cross-modal mappings that link sound features to corresponding visual characteristics. Finally, *customization* plays a complementary role, allowing users to tailor the visualization of specific audio features to their preferences.

Soundsketcher draws both on digital signal processing techniques and deep learning techniques to arrive at perceptually and culturally meaningful visualisations of sound sequences. In the following Subsections (3.3, 3.4, 3.5) three different visualisations explored in Soundsketcher will be outlined. Section 4 will present the simple line sketching methodology in more detail. The Soundsketcher application is available at this [link](#).

3.3 Line sketching based on audio features

Soundsketcher translates audio into visual representations by mapping extracted features of small audio frames to vertical line characteristics such as y-axis position, length, width, angle, and color saturation and lightness. The system extracts both low-level features (e.g., spectral centroid, flux) and high-level perceptual features (e.g., loudness, sharpness). In Figure 1 (first row) an example of a line sketch is illustrated.

Initial versions of the system relied on simple one-to-one mappings of audio features to line characteristics like spectral centroid to x axis position, loudness to line length, periodicity to line angulativity etc; on several occasions, this approach proved inadequate for fully capturing our listening experience. Instead, a more effective strategy involves combining multiple features in order to generate a richer and more representative visual form. This multidimensional mapping ensures that complex auditory characteristics are reflected in the resulting graphics, enhancing the perceptual coherence of the visualization. The line sketching approach will be further discussed in Subsection 4.1.

3.4 Sound segmentation

A key limitation of frame-based analysis is that it does not interpret sounds as cohesive sound objects, but rather as isolated fragments mapped individually to visual elements. While effective for extracting fine-grained features, this approach fails to align with how the human brain perceives sound—not as disconnected frames, but as holistic sound events [27, 28]. To address this, we are exploring structural analysis techniques that go beyond frame-based segmentation.

To identify distinct sound objects, we employ a two-stage clustering approach using the embeddings of Wav2Vec 2.0 [29] and CLAP [30] models. First, we extract high-resolution embeddings from Wav2Vec (40ms analysis window) [31]. We then determine the optimal number of clusters through cluster analysis techniques like silhouette analysis, gap statistics, etc., before performing initial segmentation. Next, we apply CLAP embeddings to the segmented parts, conducting a vector similarity comparison between adjacent segments. If the cosine similarity exceeds a predefined threshold (0.8), we merge the clusters, refining the sound object boundaries.

In Figure 1 (second row), we present a segmentation of a sound sequence into consecutive time spans, where similar sound segments are represented using the same colors.

3.5 Semantic Sound Identification

Beyond structural segmentation, semantic identification plays a crucial role in making sound objects more interpretable. CLAP is a deep learning model designed to learn audio representations by leveraging natural language descriptions and to align audio and text [30]; it performs zero-shot classification on one-second audio frames, assigning multiple tags per category to different regions of the sound. This enables a shift from purely signal-driven segmentation to a context-aware grouping, providing a more intuitive representation of sound.

CLAP, however, has been primarily trained on user-provided tags, limiting its semantic understanding to the vocabulary available in its training data. It focuses on identifying sound sources than sound impressions, making it well-suited for tagging known instruments or environmental noises but less effective at capturing timbral and perceptual characteristics such as brightness, roughness, or density. This limitation becomes especially apparent in electronic and acousmatic music, where novel, synthesized sounds do not always align with predefined sound categories.

In Figure 1 (third row), we present a segmentation and tagging of the same audio excerpt, illustrating how CLAP assigns labels based on its training data. Despite the model being biased toward tag-based classifications, it manages to partially capture abstract sonic qualities (see tags in Figure 1). Fine-tuning and retraining CLAP with a dataset that emphasizes semantic descriptors, would allow for a more perceptually relevant classification of sound qualities.

4. SOUNDSKETCHER - AN ILLUSTRATIVE

Figure 1. The three component models of Soundsketcher applied on a single stream of sound events

EXAMPLE

4.1 Visualizing Sound Through Line Structures

4.1.1 Line sketching

The Soundsketcher back-end employs a detailed feature extraction process to capture both low-level and high-level characteristics of the audio. The analysis is conducted on overlapping segments of 2048 samples with a hop length of 1024 in the time domain, ensuring a fine-grained representation of the audio signal. This extraction process relies on a combination of specialized libraries and plugins to analyze different aspects of the sound. The code for the entire workflow can be found on [GitHub](#).

Low-level audio features, such as spectral centroid, spectral flux, and zero-crossing rate, are extracted using libraries like Librosa [32], Aubio [33], and Sonic Visualiser [23] (utilizing VAMP plug-ins). These features describe the spectral, temporal and spectrotemporal properties of the sound, offering insights into its frequency distribution and time-based variations.

To incorporate aspects of human perception, high-level features such as loudness, sharpness, and roughness are extracted using Mosquito. While these features provide a closer link to how listeners experience sound in terms of intensity, texture, and clarity, they do not fully capture the complexity of auditory perception and struggle to generalize efficiently to unfamiliar sounds. Instead, they serve as an approximation, helping to bridge the gap between signal-based analysis and human auditory interpretation. Achieving a truly perceptually relevant representation remains an ongoing challenge.

4.1.2 Audio-visual one-to-one mapping

Once extracted, the audio features are used to determine the characteristics of the graphical representation. The system allows users to define their own mappings, selecting from various feature-to-visual transformations. Based on insights from the existing bibliography, we provide a set of default mapping suggestions, which serve as a starting point for meaningful representations. These predefined mappings are demonstrated in Table 1, illustrating how specific audio features can be translated into visual elements.

4.1.3 Audio feature combinations

To improve the accuracy of the graphical representation, we employ feature combinations rather than relying solely on one-to-one mappings. As demonstrated in Figure 2, different feature mappings introduce specific limitations, highlighting the need for refinement and further investigation.

In the first row of Figure 2, we observe the effect of using spectral centroid for the vertical position of lines and loudness to determine line length. While loudness ensures that louder sounds are visually represented with greater size, it seems unintuitive in depicting harmonic sounds. For instance, a loud sustained pitched sound (see sine, sawtooth and square wave sounds in Figure 2), may result in an overly thick graphical shape whereas listeners may find more appropriate a plain line. To address this, we introduce a periodicity-dependent weighting factor that modulates the impact of loudness on line length, i.e., loudness affects line length only in non-harmonic sounds.

$$\text{Line Length} = \text{Loudness} \times (1 - P) \quad (1)$$

where P is yin periodicity, $0 \leq P \leq 1$, with $P = 1$ signifying purely harmonic sounds and $P = 0$ representing white noise.

Moving to the second row of Fig. 2, we apply the loudness-periodicity combination while still using spectral centroid for y -axis positioning. Here, we see an improvement in the shape size distribution, as pitched sounds no longer appear excessively large. The vertical placement, however, of pitched sounds remains problematic, as a sawtooth wave playing an octave lower than the sinusoidal sound is positioned higher on the y -axis. This is because spectral centroid reflects spectral content rather than fundamental pitch, leading to a misrepresentation of perceived pitch height.

In the third row, we use the fundamental frequency (F_0) as the sole determinant for y -axis positioning. This correctly places pitched sounds in accordance with their fundamental frequency, but it introduces a new issue: noisy sounds lack a clear fundamental frequency, causing them to be randomly scattered in the y -axis (F_0 is ineffective for noisy or inharmonic textures) [34].

To address this, in the fourth row, we introduce periodicity (P) as a weighting factor, dynamically balancing the influence of the fundamental frequency (F_0) and spectral centroid (SC).

$$Y \text{ axis position} = F_0 \times P + SC \times (1 - P) \quad (2)$$

This effect of this formula is giving priority to fundamental frequency (F_0) detection for pitched sounds and spectral centroid for noisy sounds. Sounds with indeterminate pitch in between the two extremes are still not well represented by the above formula and are currently studied in the context of this project.

Finally, in the fifth row, we apply periodicity to color saturation and angle randomness, reinforcing the perceptual distinction between pitched and noisy sounds. Here, harmonic sounds appear with brighter tones, while noisy sounds are duller (more saturated) and line angles are random, visually emphasizing their underlying spectral structure.

The explored feature combinations highlight the need to integrate multiple descriptors for a more perceptually accurate sound representation. Future studies will further investigate additional mappings, incorporating features like roughness into visual line parameters to refine sound visualization, enhancing both analytical accuracy and perceptual coherence.

4.2 Creative Extensions

Beyond core feature-to-visual mappings, Soundsketcher offers additional sketching options, enabling alternative representations and experimentation with audiovisual relationships. These features introduce variability, structural diversity, and even sound generation possibilities.

One such option the Randomizer generates random associations between audio features and line characteristics, serving as a serendipitous tool for exploring unexpected yet insightful mappings.

Another visualization method involves Polygons (Figure 3, row 5), where each audio frame is represented as a shape with a variable number of corners (ranging from 3 to 10), effectively capturing spectral and dynamic variations. However, it may be better suited for sound objects rather than individual frames, offering a more structured representation at a larger scale.

A different technique, data point connection, generates ten individual data points per frame, which are then linked together, creating an envelope-like effect (Figure 3, row 2). While this method is useful for capturing fine details within a sound, the transition between frames with distinct characteristics can sometimes appear abrupt, making continuity an area for further refinement.

Apart from creative audio-visual mappings, Soundsketcher incorporates basic sound generation capabilities, allowing users to listen to sonifications emerging from the visual sketches. Sound generation is implemented through granular synthesis and oscillator parameter modulation. In granular synthesis, visual attributes control grain speed (perceived as pitch), loudness, and spread, while in oscillator modulation, they affect frequency and amplitude.

These extra sketching and sound generation options expand the expressive potential of Soundsketcher, offering users more flexibility and creative possibilities in how they visualize and interact with sound.

4.3 Discussion and future directions

Our current approach, based on frame-by-frame analysis and direct feature mapping, presents several limitations that affect the perceptual accuracy of visual representations. The main issue is that this method treats sound as a sequence of isolated frames rather than a cohesive structure. While enabling fine-grained analysis, it fails to reflect how the human brain perceives sound—not as disconnected snapshots, but as continuous, structured events with inherent meaning.

To address this issue, we are exploring sound object-based segmentation as a more perceptually meaningful alternative (see Subsection 3.3). We hope that this approach will enable a transition from strictly signal-driven analysis to a structured method, better aligning with the way sounds are perceived in a musical or acousmatic context.

In parallel, semantic sound identification remains a key focus for future development. While current visualization methods rely on low- and mid-level descriptors, semantic labeling offers a more intuitive representation. Models like CLAP provide a strong foundation for audio-text alignment but prioritize source identification over detailed semantic descriptors. To address this, we plan to develop a structured dictionary of semantic terms and explore re-training CLAP to better recognize and categorize higher-level perceptual and contextual attributes of sound objects.

A major challenge in our current approach is the lack of stream separation. Frame-based segmentation does not distinguish overlapping sound sources, leading to potential misrepresentations in the visual output. Addressing this requires AI-based stream separation techniques, such as deep learning models like Demucs [35] and Open-Unmix [36],

Figure 2. Soundsketcher line sketches for a simple audio sequence consisting of electronic generated sounds. From spectrogram to graphic representations sound qualities are depicted gradually in a more intuitive manner. See text for more details. (Line L: line length, Line W: line width, Color S: color saturation, Angle: random line angle, SC: Spectral Centroid, F0: Crepe F0, P: Yin Periodicity)

Figure 3. Some creative sketches by Soundsketcher for the soundfile presented in Figure 2

which have shown promising results in source separation. Integrating these models could improve the distinction of individual sound streams, enabling a more accurate and structured visualization of complex auditory environments or overlapping sound structures.

Moving forward, we aim to enrich frame-based analysis by incorporating a sound-object approach, integrating semantic identification and stream separation for more perceptually meaningful representations. While initial applications in creative and educational contexts have been promising, formal user evaluation is still needed. Upcoming crossmodal experiments and participatory design sessions with musicians and sound artists will assess the system's intuitiveness and refine its mapping strategies.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Soundsketcher represents a significant step toward bridging sound analysis and visualization by leveraging perceptually and cognitively informed mappings. By automating the representation of sound objects through aural scores, it offers an innovative alternative to traditional and manually crafted graphical notations. Its ability to extract and translate key audio features into visual elements enhances both analytical and creative applications, making it a versatile tool for music researchers, composers, and performers.

Despite its advancements, challenges remain, particularly in stream separation and the identification of distinct sound objects within complex auditory environments. Future integration of deep learning models and AI-driven auditory scene analysis promises to enhance Soundsketcher's accuracy and adaptability across diverse musical contexts. As the tool evolves, it will not only refine sound visualization but also contribute to broader discussions on the intersection of perception, notation, and the representation of mu-

sical sound.

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